

INTERMITTENT OPERATION OF A 55KW PROTON EXCHANGE MEMBRANE ELECTROLYZER: TEST PROTOCOLS AND EXPERIMENTAL INSIGHTS ON SYSTEM FLEXIBILITY, EFFICIENCY AND DURABILITY

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ABSTRACT

With its ability to decarbonize industrial activities and mitigate intermittency issues linked to the integration of renewable energies in the grids, green hydrogen holds very strong assets for accelerating the energy transition. This process can be achieved through electrolysis allowing the production of a clean and renewable hydrogen when the electrical source comes from a renewable energy, intermittent by nature, whilst most systems are currently designed to operate at nominal capacity and constant load. Current literature has shown that the intermittent operation of an electrolyzer necessarily implies losses on different performance aspects [1] [2] [3] [4]. Even though these issues have gained interest over the last decade, the behavior of electrolyzers subjected to such conditions has not been sufficiently investigated within the scientific community and few quantitative assessment of the associated impacts, especially at pilot/large scale, have been reported from current literature. This study aims at experimentally evaluating the ability of a commercial 55kW PEM electrolyzer to withstand harsh dynamic on/off and fluctuating load conditions and the impacts on the key performance indicators identified as the most sensitive to intermittency. Harmonized test protocols from [5] were used as a guideline and adapted to the specific needs of this case study.

Keywords: PEM electrolyzer, intermittency, performances, experimental characterization.

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